

Mechanism of Phase Transfer Agent aided Free Radical Polymerisation. Part-II†. Polymerisation of Methyl Methacrylate in Unstirred Systems

G. N. GUPTA and B. M. MANDAL*

Department of Physical Chemistry, Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Jadavpur, Calcutta-700 032

The kinetics of phase transfer (PT) agent aided free radical polymerisation of methyl methacrylate (MMA) has been investigated at 60° using $K_2S_2O_8$ initiator and tetrabutylammonium bromide (Bu_4NBr) PT agent and ethyl acetate solvent under unstirred condition. The rate of polymerisation (R_p) was found to be proportional to $[K_2S_2O_8]^{0.6} [Bu_4NBr] [M]$ when the volume of the aqueous phase (V_w) was small compared to the volume of the organic phase (V_o), V_w/V_o being 0.1. R_p was also found to be dependent on V_w/V_o under otherwise same experimental conditions. The reaction order with respect to V_w/V_o was found to be 0.15. The results fit in a reaction mechanism that considers the phase transferred $S_2O_8^{2-}$ as the initiator at low V_w/V_o , while at high V_w/V_o some initiation occurring also through phase transferred $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ needs to be considered.

THE PT agent aided free radical polymerisation of vinyl monomers using water soluble persulfates as initiators and crown ethers or quaternary ammonium salts (QX) as PT agents has attracted considerable interest in recent years by virtue of the rapid rate of polymerisation attained even at lower temperatures¹⁻⁵. Two mechanisms have been suggested for this type of polymerisation^{5,6}.

Mechanism 1 involves the transfer of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ from the aqueous phase to the monomer containing organic phase by PT agents (equation 2) followed by the decomposition of the initiator in the organic phase (equation 3) and initiation of polymerisation (equation 4).

Mechanism 1 :

followed by propagation and mutual bimolecular termination of polymer radicals (where, the subscripts (o) and (w) refer to the organic phase and aqueous phase, respectively).

Mechanism 2, on the other hand, considers that initiation of polymerisation occurs predominantly by phase transferred $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ rather than by phase transferred $S_2O_8^{2-}$.

Mechanism 2 :

followed by reaction (4) etc.

According to mechanism 2, some of the $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ generated in the aqueous phase from $S_2O_8^{2-}$ ion gets transferred to the monomer containing organic phase by the Q^+ ion and starts polymerisation there⁶. Unlike the phase transfer of $S_2O_8^{2-}$ (equation 2) that of $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ (equation 7) is irreversible, because the latter being very reactive gets converted to different species by way of addition to monomer (equation 4).

In a recent work from this laboratory, it was shown that under well stirred conditions polymerisation takes place predominantly according to mechanism 2, particularly when V_w/V_o is not too low ($V_w/V_o > 0.25$)⁶. There was undoubtedly some polymerisation according to mechanism 1 but its contribution was low since the amount of phase transferred $S_2O_8^{2-}$ (equation 2) was low indeed. It therefore follows that lower the value of V_w/V_o greater is the contribution of mechanism 1, and in an unstirred system it is likely that polymerisation may proceed exclusively according to mechanism 1 at very low values of V_w/V_o .

It is the purpose of this paper to show that such an expectation is fulfilled. To this end, kinetic studies of polymerisation of MMA under unstirred condition was undertaken and reported in this paper. The two phase reaction mixtures were, of course, equilibrated prior to the start of polymerisation. Jayakrishnan and Shah performed essentially similar experiments⁶. However, some of their results appear unusual as would be described later. It should be noted, as pointed out earlier⁶, that the experimental procedure adopted by Jaya-

† For Part-I see Ref. 6.

krishnan and Shah⁵ lacked rigour. Apart from the fact that the ionic strength and pH of the systems were not maintained constant by them, the R_p values reported by them were likely to be in error since these were calculated from single experiments on polymer yields in a given time, while the polymerisation reactions were conducted without removing the inhibitor and oxygen from the systems completely. Under these experimental conditions, polymerisation will be preceded by induction periods which will vary from experiment to experiment and R_p 's would therefore be in error. In the present work, all the precautions necessary to eliminate the sources of error mentioned above have been undertaken.

Experimental

MMA was freed from inhibitor by repeated washing with 5% NaOH solution followed by distilled water, dried over CaCl_2 and distilled under reduced pressure. Freshly distilled monomer was always used. Ethyl acetate (EtOAc) was distilled using a 1 m long fractionating column packed with 3 mm porcelein rings, and the fraction b.p. 77° was used. Sources and purification of all other reagents have been described⁶. Industrial grade distilled water was double-distilled in an all-glass apparatus and used.

Method: Monomer, solvent, initiator, PT agent and other reagents were charged in Corning glass tubes fitted with A-10 standard joints. The reaction mixtures were thoroughly degassed in a high vacuum line through three freeze-thaw cycles. The tubes were evacuated to 2×10^{-5} Torr and sealed. The two phase reaction mixtures were equilibrated at room temperature ($\sim 30^\circ$) by rotating the tubes end over end in a mechanical rotary shaker for 1 h, and then placed in a thermostatic bath at 60° and left undisturbed for a predetermined time period. The sealed tubes were then chilled, broken open and their contents poured into ice-cold methanol containing a trace of hydroquinone. In some situations when a colloidal polymer precipitate was obtained, the polymer was coagulated by controlled addition of a few drops of concentrated HCl. The polymers were filtered, washed thoroughly with water, dried in an oven at $\sim 70^\circ$ for 3 days. Initial experiments showed that under the above experimental conditions polymerisation took place without any induction period. Subsequently, therefore, the R_p for a given polymerisation recipe was derived from a single experiment measuring the polymer yield in a predetermined time. Occasionally, the results were checked by repeat experiments and the reproducibility was found to be good (within $\pm 5\%$).

Results and Discussion

The yields of polymer at 60° for the fixed concentration of Bu_4NBr at 0.005 M and varying

$\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ concentration (0.0005-0.04 M) at some predetermined times are given in Table 1 and those for the fixed concentration of $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ at 0.005 M and varying concentration of Bu_4NBr (0.002-0.04 M) in Table 2. The V_w/V_0 for these series of experiments was low, being 0.1. pH of the aqueous

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF TWO PHASE POLYMERISATION OF MMA

Temp. = 60°; recipe: EtOAc 8.2 ml, MMA 1.8 ml, aqueous phase 0.5 ml; $[\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}] = 0.005 \text{ M}$; ionic strength (μ) = 0.325 maintained by K_2SO_4 ; aqueous phase buffered by KHCO_3 (2%, w/v)

$[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8]$ M	Time of polymerisation min	Yield %	$K_p[\text{Q}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^\omega$
0.04	240	7.06	5.74×10^{-3}
0.03	240	9.28	4.04×10^{-3}
0.02	355	9.47	2.02×10^{-3}
0.01	515	10.29	1.18×10^{-3}
0.005	515	8.48	8.74×10^{-4}
0.0005	515	2.04	4.04×10^{-5}

* See text.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF TWO PHASE POLYMERISATION OF MMA

Temp. = 60°; recipe: EtOAc 8.2 ml, MMA 1.8 ml, aqueous phase 0.5 ml; $[\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8] = 0.005 \text{ M}$; ionic strength (μ) = 0.255 maintained by KBr; aqueous phase buffered by KHCO_3 (2%, w/v)

$[\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}]$ M	Time of polymerisation min	Yield %	$K_p[\text{Q}^+][\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^\omega$
0.04	215	16.76	3.65×10^{-3}
0.03	255	16.81	3.11×10^{-3}
0.02	415	14.89	1.86×10^{-3}
0.01	515	8.65	4.62×10^{-4}
0.005	515	5.69	3.04×10^{-4}
0.002	515	3.56	1.48×10^{-4}
0.000	515	1.86	—

* See text.

phase was maintained constant by KHCO_3 (2%, w/v). The ionic strengths of the aqueous solutions were maintained constant by KBr for the Bu_4NBr concentration variation series and by K_2SO_4 for the $\text{K}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$ concentration variation series. These data (Tables 1 and 2) were used to find the order of the reaction with respect to $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$ and $[\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}]$ as shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Also Fig 3. shows that the reaction order with respect to $[\text{M}]$ is 1. Thus

$$R_p \propto [\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]^0 \text{ } ^\omega [\text{Bu}_4\text{NBr}] [\text{M}] \quad (8)$$

where, $[\text{M}]$ is the monomer concentration.

Formerly, Jayakrishnan and Shah⁵ performed similar experiments using ammonium persulphate initiator and hexadecyl pyridinium chloride PT agent. They found that R_p increased initially with $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$, reached a maximum and then fell off at large concentrations of $[\text{S}_2\text{O}_8^{2-}]$, and with regard to the effect of $[\text{QX}]$ on R_p they observed an increase in R_p with increase in $[\text{QX}]$ and then a leveling off effect at high concentrations of QX. These observations are in conflict with those made by us. However, as mentioned in the introduction, the

Fig. 1. Relationship between R_p and $[S_2O_8^{2-}]$; recipe as in Table 1. Filled circles are data of repeat experiments.

Fig. 2. Relationship between R_p and $[Bu_4NBr]$; recipe as in Table 2.

Fig. 3. Relationship between R_p and monomer concentration; recipe: organic phase 5 ml, aqueous phase 0.5 ml; $[Bu_4NBr] = 0.02 \text{ M}$; $[K_2S_2O_8] = 0.005 \text{ M}$; $KH_2O_8 = 2\%$ (w/v); $\mu = 0.255$; temp. = 60° .

experimental results of Jayakrishnan and Shah are not reliable for reasons already mentioned⁶. We attempted to repeat their experiments at constant pH and ionic strength. Unfortunately, however, these experiments could not be performed because the quaternary salt in question, viz. hexadecyl pyridinium chloride precipitated out as the buffering as well as neutral electrolytes were added into the solution for the stated purpose. However, the rate law (equation 8) could be explained if mechanism 1 operates. Jayakrishnan and Shah derived the following equation for R_p based on mechanism 1 (Ref. 5),

$$R_p = \frac{k_p(2k_dK_p)^{\frac{1}{2}} [Q^+]_{\text{total}} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{\frac{1}{2}} [M]}{k_t^{\frac{1}{2}} \{1 + 2K_p [Q^+]_w [S_2O_8^{2-}]_w\}} \quad (9)$$

where, k_p and k_t are the rate constants for propagation and termination reactions, respectively. This equation results following some approximations which are valid only if the extent of phase transfer is small and the volumes of the two phases are equal. But under such conditions,

$$2K_p [Q^+]_w [S_2O_8^{2-}]_w \ll 1 \quad (10)$$

Jayakrishnan and Shah⁶ used equation (9) to explain their unusual R_p results for the persulphate concentration variation series assuming $2K_p [Q^+]_w [S_2O_8^{2-}]_w \gg 1$ at higher concentrations of $S_2O_8^{2-}$. But as we have just pointed out, under this latter condition equation (9) does not hold good.

If the inequality (10) applies under the experimental conditions used by us equation (9) reduces to equation (11),

$$R_p \propto [Q^+]_{\text{total}} [S_2O_8^{2-}]^{0.5} [M] \quad (11)$$

and this is precisely what has been observed by us in this work. We have previously shown that the amount of phase transferred persulphate is very small⁶ and therefore, it is reasonable to assume that the inequality (10) applies. Additionally, an indirect evidence may be presented in this regard. Fig. 4 shows the R_p results for varying concentration of an organic solvent soluble persulphate, viz. tricapyrylmethylammonium persulphate, also called Aliquat[®] persulphate ($AQ_2S_2O_8$). Considering that all the polymer yields reported in Tables 1 and 2 are effected by phase transferred persulphate, Fig. 4 may be used[†] to calculate the concentrations of phase transferred persulphate. i.e. $[AQ_2S_2O_8]_o$ for experiments reported in Tables 1 and 2. Fig. 4 yields the relation $R_p = 3.49 \times 10^{-8} [AQ_2S_2O_8]_o^{\frac{1}{2}}$.

Considering equilibrium (2)

$$[AQ_2S_2O_8]_o = K_p [Q^+]_w^2 [S_2O_8^{2-}]_w \quad (12)$$

Thus, dividing $[AQ_2S_2O_8]_o$ by $[Q^+]_w$ the value of $K_p [Q^+]_w [S_2O_8^{2-}]_w$ may be obtained. The values thus obtained are included also in Tables 1 and 2. It is evident that the values are much less than 1 so that equation (11) is valid in our case.

[†] It has been reported that k_d of $Q_2S_2O_8$ in organic medium is independent of the size of Q^+ (Ref. 3).

Fig. 4. Homogeneous phase polymerisation of MMA using $AQ_2S_2O_8$ initiator; recipe: $[MMA]=3.40 \text{ M}$ in $EtOAc$; temp. = 60° .

Effect of the variation of V_w/V_o on R_p : Although equation (9) is strictly valid when $V_w/V_o=1$, it can be safely used for lower values of V_w/V_o provided these are not exceedingly low. In other words, one should not see a dependence of R_p on V_w/V_o over a wide range. However, Fig. 5 shows that even in an unstirred system, R_p slowly increases with increase in V_w/V_o under otherwise same experimental conditions. Treatment of the data given in Fig. 5 gives $R_p \propto (V_w/V_o)^{0.15}$. These results could be rationalised only if it is considered that even in an unstirred system some polymerisation takes place according to mechanism 2. Some of the $SO_4^{\cdot-}$ generated in the aqueous phase is transported to the organic phase by Q^+ ion through the small interfacial area of the unstirred biphasic system. For the somewhat sparingly water soluble monomer used here the transported radical may also be the sulphate group ended oligomer radical. Mechanism 2 predicts $R_p \propto (V_w/V_o)^{0.5}$ while mechanism 1 predicts $R_p \propto (V_w/V_o)^0$. An intermediate situation may find the order with respect to (V_w/V_o) anywhere between 0 and 0.5. As has been argued before in this paper and also elsewhere⁶ an increase in V_w/V_o results in an increase in contribution due to mechanism 2.

Fig. 5. Dependence of R_p on V_w/V_o : the closed circles refer to R_p in the organic phase only, and the open circles refer to the total R_p . The variation shown is based on data of two experiments for each point conducted at 1 month interval; recipe: $[MMA]=3.40 \text{ M}$ in $EtOAc$; $[Bu_4NBr]=0.02 \text{ M}$; $[K_2S_2O_8]=0.005 \text{ M}$; $[KHCO_3]=2\%$ (w/v); $\mu=0.255$; temp. = 60° .

Conclusions: It may thus be concluded that in unstirred systems at low values of V_w/V_o (say 0.1) the polymerisation proceeds according to mechanism 1. Contribution to R_p from mechanism 2 being negligible under such circumstances, while for higher values of V_w/V_o (say 1) some contribution by mechanism 2 also occurs.

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